

Neuro Pedagogical Fundamentals of Preschool and Primary School Children Emotional Intelligence Development

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Abstract: *The discussion of psychologists and physiologists on the work of the brain as the center for the formation of emotions and feelings, the center of memory and planning of future actions has been highlighted. Taking into account the main provisions of neuroscientists' works, the gender characteristics of the emotional reactions of boys and girls have been revealed in accordance with differences in the structure and work of their brains. This gave the grounds for the conclusion that in order to form the correct behavior of the child in society, it is necessary to enhance his interaction experience in it, develop strong-willed efforts and ensure the full development of a rational brain. of The vast majority of junior schoolchildren need to have their level of emotional intelligence to be corrected. The main source of intellectual, moral and aesthetic feelings as components of the emotional intelligence of preschool and primary school children is gaming and educational activities, during which all kinds of feelings that affect the children's adaptation to the new living conditions are being developed. If a child does not reach a sufficient level of emotional development by the age of 10-11, which is distinguished by the greatest plasticity of the cerebral cortex and almost unlimited intellectual capabilities, then at the later age his life cannot be successful and comfortable due to numerous misunderstandings with himself and others, close and strangers.*

Keywords: *Emotional intelligence, physiological mechanisms of emotions, brain as the head of emotional behavior, conditions for the intellectual activity development, gender characteristics of emotional reactions, congenital makings of emotional sensitivity, features of junior students emotional intelligence.*

How to cite: Kotyk, T., Sichka, V., Ragozina, V., Vasilieva, S., Havrysh, N., & Ponomarenko, T. (2021). Neuro Pedagogical Fundamentals of Preschool and Primary School Children Emotional Intelligence Development. *BRAIN. Broad Research in Artificial Intelligence and Neuroscience*, 12(4), 278-296. <https://doi.org/10.18662/brain/12.4/250>

Introduction

Each person can succeed in life, but not everyone uses all his natural potential for this. Everyone understands that in order to be successful, you need to learn, but nowadays it is not so important to gain knowledge, as to acquire the ability to apply them quickly and creatively, adapting to new fleeting conditions.

In the New Ukrainian School, the ability to learn is stated as one of the most important skills obtained in the educational process, which must be formed during the years of study in elementary school (Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, 2016). Therefore, teachers drew attention to the related sciences research, in particular physiology and neuropsychology, on increasing the activation and performance of the human brain in order to use more effectively this most important organ for the production of intelligence and transfer the obtained knowledge to the practical application area (Komogorova, 2021; Kotyk, 2020; Kucher & Hrishchenko, 2020; Maksymchuk, 2020a, 2020b; Melnyk et al., 2019, 2021; Sheremet, 2019).

In the twentieth century, much attention was paid to the study of intelligence and its varieties, which made it possible to realize the huge human abilities potential. Thus, the specialist in age psychology Gardner (1983), the founder of the theory of multiple intelligence, described a dozen different types of intelligence that provide the ability to interact effectively with practical life challenges.

Therefore, the brain was studied not only to understand the causes of brain diseases, but also to found out the answers to the question how the brain affects the intellectual development and human life as a whole.

The physiological mechanisms of emotions were studied by psychologist William James (1893), who concluded that emotions are a mental reflection of physiological changes in the activity of blood vessels, glands, muscles, etc., which occur in the body under the influence of external stimuli, and a direct understanding of that excitement at the moment of its realization is an emotion. According to the researchers all organic changes realized by man as emotions associated with changes in peripheral blood circulation, and feelings arising in this state, are a manifestation of spiritual principles.

In return, physiologist Cannon (1915) refuted this theory, experimentally proving that internal organs are insensitive structures and are not able to reflect all those differences observed in various emotions that

arise quickly and develop very rapidly, that is, there is no causal relationship between the feeling of internal body reactions of the and experiences of emotions.

As a result of P. Bard's physiological experiments (1928), it was found out that emotional processes determine and regulate human behavior depending on the nature and intensity of emotional experiences and that emotions can be controlled by involving the central nervous system. There are localized centers in the brain that control emotional reactions. In the process of human development they have hardly changed and are not much different from the corresponding areas of the animal brain.

The brain as a physiological center for the formation of emotions

The brain is an extremely complex mechanism responsible for human survival. It not only controls all processes in the body: the work of internal organs, movements, perception of information, but also corresponds by emotions and feelings on external stimuli and is a memory and future acts planning center (Svaab, 2017).

Nowadays the three human brains coexistence theory, which simultaneously interact during decision-making process, action planning is popular.

According to the three human brains theory, the lower part of the brain is the base for all human instincts: the stem and the cerebellum. This brain is called old, or sensory. It is responsible for the main functions of the body: heartbeat, breathing, balance, vascular tone, blood pressure, bodily sensations and controls survival instincts (safety and fears), continuation of the genus (love, family creation), division of all into one's own and others.

The middle part of the brain historically developed later. This brain part is called emotional, since the result of its work is an emotion-based decision making.

This part contains short and long memories that help understanding and perception, and this is the exact place where intuition is born.

The cerebral cortex is called the new or rational brain, responsible for comprehension, pondering information. This is the center of control over actions. Thanks to the work of the rational brain emotions do not prevail over the mind which makes it possible to make balanced and meaningful decisions in different situations of interpersonal interaction. To activate this part of the brain, unlike the previous two ones, it is necessary to make strong-willed efforts that is, to get out of the comfort zone of

automatic actions controlled by an emotional state. Such action automatism on emotions "without brakes" creates preconditions for the occurrence of conflicts and social sensitivity blunting, which is just dangerous for human life success.

Each part of the brain in its own way, according to its functional purpose, helps to make a decision, to plan the sequence of actions. Thus, the first reaction to the stimulus occurs at the level of basic instincts of "stand", "fight", "run away", accompanied by basic emotions of joy, anger or fear. In parallel, almost simultaneously, the emotional part of the brain is activated, analyzing emotions. The lack of experience, memories and digested models of interaction makes it difficult to make the right decisions regarding the following actions, which causes the child's misconduct in society.

To comprehend and think about the received information, the child needs to activate a rational brain that is not yet developed enough, and make strong-willed efforts that do not arise without positive stimulation. Since the brain is extremely flexible, its formation transpires under the influence of experience and training. Considering this human brain feature, the well-known neurophysiologist Marian Diamond (Webcast-legacy Departmental, 2007) noted that the physical mechanism of child genius can be created by means of mental exercises, that is, the brain needs constant tension to solve complex problems in order to reach the peak of its capabilities.

So, in order to form the correct behavior of the child in society, it is necessary to form the interaction experience, develop strong-willed efforts and ensure the full development of a rational brain.

The brain, as a conductor of emotional behavior, responding to information from the environment and subjective experiences, sends signals to the endocrine, cardiovascular, respiratory systems about the need for reconfiguration in work and the urgent production of vital substances. Any emotion is accompanied by universal signs for all people: activation of the nervous system and the appearance of biologically active substances in the blood that change the internal organs activity and cause an increase in heart rate, blood pressure, breathing rate, etc. Thus, increasing blood pressure can be a consequence of person's inability to master their negative emotions and their manifestations, unwillingness to focus on a constructive problem solution, again and again experiencing anxiety, panic, fear. Owing to high blood pressure, cognitive abilities are reduced in the arteries: perception, attention, memory, decision-making. Under the action of adrenaline, the

work of the heart, muscles increases, vascular tone increases, glucose level increases which either increases the overall person's activity, or stops it completely. Such conditions can be dangerous to human life and health, so the body launches self-regulation mechanisms from stress. If this is enough, then the anxiety subsides and the person goes out of stress. If the stress factor continues to act, then all body systems are activated as much as possible: mental, muscular, strong-willed, which contributes to the gradual normalization of the post-stress state. The subsequent action of a negative stimulus leads to the stage of depletion of the body reserves, which can cause numerous diseases.

The brain processes all signals acting on humans in the environment, recognizes threats and dangers, gives the appropriate body systems commands to develop the necessary chemicals and thus activates all reserves to avoid danger.

It exhibits extraordinary adaptive qualities, redistributing the performance of the necessary functions from damaged areas to healthy ones, that is, it has huge reserves to ensure human vital activity.

The brain always works, but not all of its areas are involved at the same time. Even during sleep, the brain processes and sorts information received throughout the day. During the day the separate nerve centers unite to perform a certain task and work in concert, until the task changes to another type of activity and the brain prioritizes the work of other centers. Instead, in order to effectively use all the reserves, it is necessary for brain to learn to analyze what is happening and make appropriate decisions in time.

The intellectual activity development conditions

Various psychological schools cannot agree on determining the optimal natural conditions for the development of the child's intellectual activity to answer the questions: "In what human state is the brain best able to learn to give the necessary commands to the body?" According to the scientists' research at the University of Chicago, it is possible even in situations of physical inactivity of a person who only monitors events, say, in front of a TV that was tested during the training of militaries, firefighters, guards, athletes. Instead, the passive monitoring of events on a TV screen by the children slows their brain development, since the brain activity decreases under the action of only one stimulus on the nervous system. So, the more time children spend at TVs, the worse they learn.

Most scientists are convinced, however, that the brain develops best in different types of practical activities, and to reach the peaks in professional intellectual activity you need to exercise at least 10,000 hours. This rule applies to all areas of activity.

The "10,000 Hours Rule" was formulated on the basis of neurophysiological anatomical studies, which showed that mental development depends not on the number of neurons in the brain, which remains sustainable after human birth, but on the number of connections between them. Up to 90% of brain neurons are formed after birth, and their number and structure directly depend on the nature of information coming to the child from the environment. Consequently, the effectiveness of brain work depends on the number of connections between neurons. The more of them, the higher the probability is that the brain will be able to find the optimal way out of any situation (Kharisova, 2011).

The more actively the child learns, the more such compounds arise. Conversely, if the brain is immersed in congestion without training or the nervous system is too excited, the connecting cells begin to die off. If the brain is used correctly, the number of neural connections may increase throughout life. The more the brain develops in youth, the better it will work in old age.

At preschool and junior school age, regular intellectual and physical activity contributes to the fact that the contacts between centers responsible for the perception and reproduction of oral and written speech are intensively formed in the cerebral cortex. Reading, solving logical problems, crosswords, puzzles, when children "break their heads", meeting with new, unknown things to solve the problem, as well as aerobic exercises, running and swimming are the most useful for the brains of children.

Neurophysiologist-innovator Marian Diamond's recent research (Webcast-legacy Departmental, 2007) confirmed a long-known fact: the development of intellectual centers of the brain depends not on genetic factors and external stimuli, but on feedback on spontaneous and expressive activity of a person. Thus, unlike passive contemplation of TV shows, working on a computer involves an active feedback between making a decision, for which the brain is responsible, and acting with a mouse click, which leads to the corresponding results.

The brain is not multitasking. It cannot perform more than two processes simultaneously involving concentration and attention because it lacks energy resources. Two tasks can be completed only with the automated

skill of one of them and the ability to switch quickly from one action to another. However, there are more errors in activity in this case than those who focus on the implementation of one task.

Gender characteristics of emotional intelligence. In the course of the development of emotional intelligence, it is necessary to take into account the gender characteristics of emotional reactions, since there is some difference in the girls' and boys' brains.

Thus, girls have slightly enlarged brain structures responsible for emotions and their memorization, so they have the ability to express emotions verbally earlier than boys. Girls are more focused on the moral content of behavior and are able to differentiate emotional states more finely. They are more accurate than boys in expressing their feelings and replace physical emotional reactions with verbal ones. Unlike girls, the boys' language centers are not developed and coordinated within them in the same way, so they use fewer words to describe their emotional state. Under the age of 10, boys and girls do not differ significantly in the manifestations of aggressive behavior: if they feel the emotion of anger, they demonstrate aggression physically. Already at the age of 12-13, girls acquire much better skills in verbal and non-verbal expression of emotions, and boys continue to use physical acts as a means of expressing anger.

The researchers of gender differences in emotional reactions (Andreeva, 2011; Nosenko & Kovryga, 2003) note that the differences between boys and girls in behavior and perception are caused not so much by physiological features, but by education and advanced ideas about the essence of male and female. For example, boys are taught that crying, fearing, showing tender feelings is not suitable for men, because they should only be courageous in showing righteous anger and aggression towards those who offend; and girls are taught that to show anger and aggression, to laugh out loud, to treat boys nicely is indecently, to control their feelings and to have endurance. In public opinion, it seems that this style of education will best help children adapt in society.

Development of children emotional intelligence

The problem of developing the emotional intelligence of the individual since the emergence of primary emotions in a child is one of the most difficult in modern psychology, since emotional processes are distinguished by short-term course, almost elusiveness, which makes it difficult to diagnose and study them. At the same time, this problem is one

of the most relevant, because emotions are the basis for a person's mental development, his spiritual and social life.

In the child mental life, the first connections with the social environment are carried out precisely due to emotions, on the basis of which mental development occurs. The emergence of primary emotions psychologists explained by the person's physiological reaction to the changes in the body as a result of the internal organs work, individual centers of the brain, central nervous system. Therefore, the primary and main function of emotions is the assessment and adaptation to certain circumstances, phenomena, events. Under certain living conditions, under the influence of education, when a child learns social values, norms and requirements, emotions acquire richer content and more complex forms of manifestation and serve as an indicator of the child's internal state.

The indexes of the development of junior students' emotional intelligence are influenced by both biological and social factors.

American psychologist William James (1893) proved that emotions arise under the influence of physiological processes in the body, therefore, the child's emotional susceptibility is partially hereditary: congenital makings of emotional sensitivity are directly related to the properties of temperament. According to the results of an empirical study, Andreeva (2011) found out that the level of child's emotional intelligence is influenced mainly by the similar quality of his mother and not the father, on the basis of which it was concluded about the non-genetic nature of the emotional intelligence transfer, because genes are inherited from parents equally.

Hence, it was noted that the emotional intelligence of the child is absorbed, brought up and developed in the nearest environment and without the influence of social factors emotional sensitivity remains poorly developed, with immature feelings.

The knowledge, skills and emotional competence necessary for social adaptation the child acquires only in the environment, where the parents are the most significant factor in the emotional impact.

According to D. Goleman (1998), the children inherit indirectly the level of parents' emotionality. The heirs are always more developed emotionally and intellectually in educated and wealthy parents than in the ignorant as well as in low-income families. The researcher affirmed that poverty destroyed children's brains and programmed a person to live in poverty. When a family loses paramount importance for a child to develop, a

group of peers, friends, classmates become a developing environment for him.

At school age not only the family but also the school is the closest environment of the child, which serves as a guide for realistic self-perception and self-assessment, which also affects the formation of mechanisms of self-regulation and self-control, gives the child confidence in interpersonal interaction. Emotional interaction with society helps to cognize the world around us, to determine a safe and dangerous environment, patterns of manifestation of phenomena and events in it. The child's emotional manifestations become deep and prolonged, if associated with his vital needs.

The emotional development of preschool and primary schoolchildren age was studied by L. Vigotsky, D. Elkonin, O. Zaporozhets, G. Kostyuk and other psychologists, which made it possible to distinguish the appearance of special emotional neoplasm in children of 7-10 years: the transition from children's emotional spontaneity to the formation of the logic of feelings.

The active child's emotional formation continues at junior school age, which is characterized by high sensibility and flexibility of all mental processes. He begins to realize the meaning of feelings, gradually acquires the ability to manage them, and therefore increases restraint, a sense of responsibility. He shows interest, trust and kindness towards other people, although he does not always interpret other people's feelings correctly. Healthy children are dominated by cheerful, joyful moods.

In the school environment of interactions with peers and adults such social emotions as selfishness and the ability to empathize develop in students. Through comprehension of one's own emotions and actions, there is a formation of self-awareness, the ability to reflect and decentralize, that is, the ability to understand the feelings of another and take into account his needs for joint activities is formed. There is hypersensitivity and vulnerability expressed in painful experiences and sincere expression of joy or sadness, pleasure or dissatisfaction. For example, students of 1-2 grades react violently and emotionally to novelties in the design of the class, new textbooks, ICT technologies. On the background of general vigor, cheerfulness, joyfulness there is a tendency to short-term and unexpected changes in mood, since in the cerebral cortex of children there are still insufficiently developed areas responsible for inhibitory processes. Junior

schoolchildren as well as preschoolers quickly get excited and quickly calm down.

Features of junior schoolchildren emotional intelligence and didactic aspects of its development. According to the results of empirical studies (Test, without date; Shpak, 2016; 2017) it was determined that only a small part of 6-9-year-old children are able to recognize and understand their own and other people's emotions, establish causal relationships between experiences and their displays, control emotions, restraining or manifesting them in accordance with the situation and norms of behavior. Such children establish emotional contact with peers and adults easily and naturally, show their empathy during communication, often acquire the status of a leader, adapt well to new conditions, contribute to the improvement of the socio-psychological climate in the team.

Instead, most junior schoolchildren have the following features of emotional intelligence:

- children are not able to identify their own and other people's emotions and do not understand the causes of their occurrence, and therefore react inadequately to the other people's emotional manifestations, with the exception of basic emotions of fear and joy;
- are not able to control their own emotions, especially negative ones, therefore they are not prone to interpersonal communication;
- are distinguished by emotional ignorance, the lack of self-motivation, empathy (Shpak, 2018).

The main source of emotions for children of preschool and primary school age is cognitive and gaming activities, communication with peers. Strong emotional genic factors for them are also the results of training and evaluation of children by the teacher, parents, and classmates.

The main source of intellectual, moral and aesthetic feelings as components of the emotional intelligence of preschool and primary school children is gaming and educational activities, during which all kinds of feelings develop.

During active cognitive activity children face problems, difficulties that they learn to overcome, making strong-willed efforts, as a result there is a new range of intellectual feelings: interest, surprise, doubt, joy, curiosity, feeling of new, etc. In older preschoolers and first-graders, such feelings arise from facts and events that can be seen and observed, so before submitting new knowledge, it is necessary to cause children's emotional attitude to it so that new knowledge is associated with positive emotions.

Children learn this knowledge better and keep it in memory longer. For the development of intellectual feelings it is important to rely on vivid ideas, visuals, which will help to establish and show cause-and-effect relationships.

For students of 1-2 grades, the introduction of game situations into the learning process helps to create a slight excitement and emotional exaltation, which will motivate them to overcome difficulties on the way to solving educational problems and achieving success. The lower the age of students, the greater value becomes a positive emotional background in the learning process to motivate students to discover new knowledge.

During joint gaming or educational activities with peers, children choose among them comrades, in cooperation with whom moral feelings of respect, support, understanding, sympathy and favor develop. Under the influence of school education, students develop a special strong-willed act, focused on meeting the interests of close ones - a moral act.

For the sake of family and friends a student can give up some of his interests, so he expects recognition from others, and therefore painfully reacts to humiliation on the part of adults and bullying on the part of other schoolchildren, showing emotional unbalance, rudeness, stubbornness, behavioral disorders. Emotional disorders of junior schoolchildren often arise due to disadaptation to a new social situation, where the conflicts of self-esteem or interpersonal type can erupt because of uncertainty, fear or misunderstandings between students. Aggression as a protective form of behavior can occur in the form of a reaction to emotional feelings such as anxiety, anger and fear.

Despite the high emotional sensitivity of younger students, it is very important from the first days of a child's stay at school to teach him to adhere to clear requirements and rules of behavior, to create a positive socio-psychological climate that will develop students' emotional and strong-willed character traits, will contribute to the formation of purposefulness, organization, discipline and perseverance. In the course of study, the learned social norm of behavior becomes a guideline in situations of choosing the right action.

Friendly relations are unstable amidst junior schoolchildren, friends change in random and subjective characteristics, among which common interests prevail in gaming activities, spending free time, selfish interest.

Forming moral feelings in preschoolers and younger schoolchildren, it is necessary to focus on their life experience, unusual events that they have experienced, vivid memories and feelings. Educational events that do not

involve examples from children's life experiences and that are not filled with their emotional experiences will not have an appropriate positive effect.

Thus, educational and training matters should be based on the life experience, emotional and sensory sphere of children.

During acquaintance with new works of art aesthetic feelings continue to develop, especially under the influence of poetic works. Rhythmic poetry, its sonority, expressiveness, figurativeness evoke emotional attitude to poems.

It is in poetic works that children better capture the emotional mood of nature descriptions, the attitude of the author to the depicted paintings and events. Under the conditions of specially organized learning, when the teacher singles out and emphasizes the aesthetic and emotional aspects of musical works and painting, children begin to understand the artistic value of works of art, can emotionally appreciate them. Without special training, children of preschool and primary school age are interested only in the plot of an art work.

In junior school, the life circumstances of a child who for the first time finds himself in an unfamiliar environment among strangers, where he/she needs to act independently, in accordance with the acquired skills and abilities, change dramatically. It is during this period that intensive emotional and strong-willed development of the child occurs. If in the preschool period children showed maximum emotional reactions and strong-willed efforts in the game and communication, then in the school the main efforts of teachers are directed to the process and result of educational activities that cause students' emotional exaltation or dissatisfaction and apathy. In preschool the child constantly interacted with his peers, and at school a first-grader feels lonely and alien, does not communicate with anyone but the teacher and very rarely, so the relationship with him is restrained and strained. In the New Ukrainian School the collective morning meetings, communication situations, paired and group teaching methods were introduced to overcome the contrast during the transition from preschool childhood to school, to facilitate the process of establishing contacts between students and the teacher, which will help relieve tension, allow to show emotions from new experiences, but within the established school rules.

In the preschool period the child directly satisfied all his desires and needs and in the process of studying at school he/she should constantly make strong-willed efforts, acting in accordance with the rules or on demand

or a sample of the teacher. Such arbitrary actions during the assimilation of knowledge, skills and abilities, which requires overcoming various obstacles in order to achieve the goal, improves the strong-willed qualities of students.

Studies of Ukrainian psychologists (Karpenko, 2017; Zarytska, 2011, etc.) have proved that elementary school students have already formed psychophysiological prerequisites for the formation of arbitrary behavior, manifestations of self-control over their own actions, deterrence of impulsive actions. It explains that the first-graders have such a mental neoplasm, as the formation and development of arbitrary behavior and mastery of the ability to subordinate direct motives to remote, and personal ones to social.

The strong-willed development of younger students is accompanied by a deterrent of sharp emotional manifestations, students stop shouting during lessons, try not to cry after failures in learning or joint activities. Young school children gradually learn to control their behavior. They try to restrain desires that do not relate to the educational process, obey the rules of the class and the teacher's requirements.

An important component in the formation of junior schoolchildren's arbitrary behavior is the education of such a character trait as endurance. At first, it appears as the ability to obey the parents' requirements, and then there is the ability to subordinate their desires to the school routine and extracurricular life.

At the same time the child's increased emotionality can develop as an expression of excessive impulsivity which prevents the steady and systematic development of endurance.

Without the correct pedagogical support for the child's emotional development, impulsivity will become its individual feature, which will prevent the child to achieve the goal in any activity.

For the first-grade students, unlike fourth-graders, the low level of almost all parameters of emotional and strong-willed development is typical, namely: discipline, perseverance, endurance, independence, courage, organization, diligence, self-control, motivation. Only the first-graders' diligence is stronger than the fourth-graders' one.

Endurance and perseverance have a more noticeable impact on the behavior of third-grade students, which enables them to overcome minor obstacles in the course of learning success. This ability is clearly manifested during homework, in depiction art lessons, in labor. It is worth noting that such emotional and strong-willed qualities as endurance, organization and

diligence do not yet receive a clearly defined development during their studies in elementary school, and remain at a low level from the first to the fourth grade.

The emotional and strong-willed efforts of younger students contribute to social adaptation during their studies in elementary school, increase motivation for learning, and therefore they gradually improve the conscious regulation of behavior and actions.

Consequently, the level of emotional intelligence of the vast majority of junior schoolchildren needs to be corrected. The presence of individual emotionally gifted children in junior school age indicates that primary school students can achieve a high level of emotional intelligence under certain conditions. Such conditions should be aimed at familiarizing students with emotions and their types, that is, the formation of emotional awareness, the ability to analyze the emotional state, their own and other people, the development of the ability to create self-motivation to manage negative emotions and the development of empathy.

The emotional and strong-willed development of younger students directly affects their adaptation capabilities and depends on them. The transition of the child to schooling, a new, unusual social situation, which also limits direct emotional manifestations, is accompanied by systematic micro-stresses, which requires the child to adapt to new conditions and requirements of life. Revealing the peculiarities of the process of studying in elementary school, psychologist Jean Piaget (1947) noted that learning takes place through assimilation and adaptation, when a student assigns valuable and important information obtained from various sources and imposes it on his own existing experience, which accordingly changes his behavior.

By the end of the first half of an academic year, first-graders should already adapt to schooling. The positive emotional attitude to school, the ability to independent educational activities without the help of adults and the ability to overcome obstacles to achieve the goal, low level of school anxiety, positive interaction with classmates and teachers, participation in school activities are the indicators of successful social adaptation.

Instead, too often at the end of first grade, most students are still at a low level of adaptation to school life, experience high levels of school anxiety, and tend to perceive most school events as threatening. The presence of aggression or slowing down, a feeling of fear, unwillingness to go to school testify the level of increased school anxiety.

The first-graders who have a low level of school adaptation do not take themselves as schoolchildren, make learning difficult, and, of course, therefore do not want to go to school. They are worried not only about this, but also of the fact that it is necessary to communicate with parents and teachers about it. Therefore, the teacher should pay special attention to expressing his attitude to students, using not official business, but an intimate-maternal style of communication, which means taking the position of the child in difficult situations. The authoritarian style, which separates the teacher from the child, is an obstacle in the child's adaptation to school, reducing the level of success and cognitive motivation.

The fourth-grade students are positive about the school, although they like it not because of participation in the educational process, but only because it is possible to communicate with classmates and teachers, feel like a student and have good school supplies. They are alarmed only by situations of communication and establishing contacts with individual classmates. The fourth-graders experience the optimal level of school anxiety, which psychologists call useful because it is a necessary condition for personal development (Starling et al., 2019).

Thus, learning in primary school is a difficult and important period in a child's life, as the daily routine, social role and social environment change abruptly, a new type of activity appears, it is learning that requires concentration, willpower, which is still underdeveloped in 6-7-year-old students. Therefore, in primary school, especially in the first and second grades, during the adaptation-play period at the lessons it is necessary to introduce game situations, use didactic games; in addition, since children still have a great need for physical activity, it is advisable not to limit it during lessons but to subordinate it to the didactic purpose. The game and motor activity of students will help awaken interest in learning, facilitate the course of adaptation to educational activities.

By the end of primary school age, the structure of emotional representations is almost completely formed, covering a generalized system of knowledge about emotions and an individual value-emotional color of each unit of knowledge acquired during the gaining their own emotional experience.

Conclusions

Consequently, the task of developing emotional intelligence is an important component of the content of primary education. Mastering it by

primary school pupils as a means of successful social interaction and cognition of themselves and others should become the most important attainment of the child in junior school age, which is especially sensitive to the assimilation of norms and rules of public communication. If the child does not reach a sufficient level of emotional development by the age of 10-11 years, which is distinguished by the greatest pliability of the cerebral cortex and almost unlimited intellectual capabilities, then at later age stages his life path cannot be successful and comfortable due to numerous misunderstandings with himself and other close people and strangers.

Primary school teachers are called not only to teach young children to read and write, but also to lay the foundation for the future formation of a holistic personality in adolescence who understands himself and others and can succeed in both independent and group collective activities.

The effectiveness of work on the development of emotional intelligence depends on a well-thought-out system of pedagogical influence, the emotional competence of the teacher and taking him into account the neuropedagogic principles of the development of emotional intelligence.

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